

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BABALOLA****FIRST NAME: DAMILARE****PROGRAM CODE: DGG****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord Microsoft 365 on Windows 10s)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Writing An Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. Rules of Thumb for Writing Academic Paper (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
4. American vs British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-33)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
6. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

Deleted: (samples below):**Deleted: A****Deleted: pages****Deleted: pages****Deleted: pages****Deleted: v****Deleted: pages****Deleted: pages****Deleted: pages****Deleted: ¶****Formatted: Font: (Default) Arial, 9 pt**

Formatted: List Paragraph, Indent: Left: 0.63 cm, Hanging: 0.63 cm, Numbered + Level: 1 + Numbering Style: 1, 2, 3, ... + Start at: 1 + Alignment: Left + Aligned at: 0.63 cm + Indent at: 1.27 cm

Deleted: fulfil

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING (ACA-401D)

1) INTRODUCTION

After several years of searching, I am excited to start my doctorate programme at EUCLID University. Having gone through the study materials for this course, I have gained more confidence that this journey will be worthwhile because the approach and methodology offered at EUCLID suit my present circumstance of combining a full-time career with academic pursuit. While recognising the commitment and time required to fulfill this ambition, I believe that EUCLID's structure and mode of presentation, including supportive faculties, will enable me not to relent on this noble pursuit.

I had previewed all the course materials and found them succinctly prepared and valuable introductions to some critical concepts that I need to familiarise myself with when preparing for my academic writing, especially as a new entry student at the doctorate (PhD) level. After going through the ACA-401D course materials, I have gained a good grasp of what is required to write a beautiful academic essay. The materials I previewed included the ACA-401/401D course pack (period 1), Basic ACA-401 Tutorial Video delivered by

Professor Laurent Cleenewerck, Instructor's Sample Review Video delivered by Dr Kabiru Gulma, Grammarly Tutorial Video and How To Use Zotero Tutorial Video.

In the following sections of this Response Paper (RP), I will highlight six areas that I found particularly helpful in my learning during this period. I will also be doing my writing using the UK conventions of grammar.

2) WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

The study material succinctly defines an academic essay as a piece of 'nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work' (EUCLID 2021, 7). This definition is a good starting point for understanding the difference between academic essays and other types of essays or write-ups. It is not surprising to note from the onset that academic writing must meet some requirements because of its major preoccupation with seeking answers that contribute to knowledge or communicating ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2021, 7).

The first section of the course pack provides useful details on the processes one can follow when preparing an academic essay. From my reading, I agree with the emphasis placed on early preparation and having a clear plan to guide my writing as a pathway for producing an excellent academic essay. According to EUCLID 2021, following this process will help me to focus and hone my thoughts and ideas about what I intend to write clearly (p. 7-9). I agree with the assertion that sufficient time to research the topic will help me attain broad and balanced perspectives and provide an array of evidence to support my views. It will also lend more credence to the analysis of the position I assert in the essay. Similarly, I agree that organising my ideas will help me keep the topic focused and arrange the key points of my essay in a logical sequence.

Also, under this section, I am provided with a refresher on three essential parts of an essay – the introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). This is a good reminder to re-orientate someone like me who had been used to writing technical and project reports in the last decade about presentation styles for an academic essay. While the conventional technical report writing approach is not dissimilar in terms of structure, I have now learnt that there is a need to possess a creative and critical mindset when preparing an academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 9). An important point of emphasis I have also taken is the need to give sufficient time to prepare my academic essay. Otherwise, it will be difficult for me to comply with the excellent suggestion of leaving the draft essay for some time and returning to it later with refreshed perspectives (EUCLID 2021, 11).

3) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING ACADEMIC PAPER

Although this section is under section one, I would like to summarise my understanding of the eight rules of thumb as part of my primary learning during this period. Firstly, it is clear that adherence to these rules will help me stay focused on my line of

argument, enable me to present the central thesis of my essay and eliminate distractions. Secondly, writing clearly without sweeping generalities is an excellent way to advance an argument in a good academic paper. This rule reinforces the need for comprehensive research and the building of evidence to support the position I wish to advance in my academic essay. Writing in clear and simple sentences will help the easy flow of my ideas rather than making them clumsy and boring. Next, I understand that while research is essential, it should not be a liberty to make my work full of quotations and repetition of others' ideas. It is also crucial that as an academic, I must hold my views in high esteem and with every sense of seriousness to ensure that every quotation adds significant value to my argument. Finally, the course strongly emphasises the dire consequence of plagiarism. Although I am aware of the consequence, the emphasis on plagiarism serves as a good reminder of what EUCLID considers plagiarism and how it is treated. For instance, I have learnt that plagiarism can occur without quotation marks or through inappropriate referencing of sources of information. Both cases can have consequences which 'may range from lowering grades on assignment to failing grade' (EUCLID 2021, 14). Giving sufficient time to edit and review the essay repeatedly is one of the recommendations suggested to guide against plagiarism.

Deleted: Euclid

4) PUNCTUATIONS

Chapter two of the course pack introduces me to the effective use of punctuation marks. While the course pack provides good examples of punctuation marks, I thought that a brief definition of punctuation marks could have helped to understand why this section is an important aspect of this course. Nevertheless, the lack of definition also helped me to consult different dictionaries to refresh my mind on the meaning of punctuation. According to Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary, punctuation is an 'act or practice of inserting standardised marks or signs in a written matter to clarify the meaning and separate structural units' (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). It is also referred to as 'the marks (such as periods and commas) in a piece of writing that makes its meaning clear and that separate it into sentences, clauses' (Britannica Dictionary, n.d.). With these definitions and the brief details provided in the course pack, I agree that it is important for a new entry into academic writing like me to have a good command of using different punctuation marks when writing academic papers. For instance, understanding the difference between colon and semicolon and when to use it can help with a logical flow of presentation in the same way that inappropriate use of apostrophes, commas or brackets in a sentence can affect the message being communicated. I also agree with EUCLID's advice to use punctuation as little as possible in sentences/phrases while retaining the intended meaning (2021, p. 16). A would-be scholar like me at the doctorate level should strictly adhere to this rule. I agree that taking on this practice will help me write good academic papers.

Commented [GK1]: This is not as per Turabian. Kindly delete!

5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

I found this section very interesting because it further enhances my understanding of the parallels between American and British English in scholarly writing. Before now, I

had thought that British English was the most acceptable, but American English seems dominant according to the reading material (EUCLID 2021, 25). It is also quite enlightening for me to see that American English has matured alongside other critical factors that have positioned the country as a leader among the global powers: the sheer size of the economy, the influence on global/international political architecture, the appeal of American popular culture (music, film, technology) and the magnitude of higher education, mass media and publishing industry (EUCLID 2021, 25), to mention a few.

While the dominance of American English is noted, it is equally important to note that there are many similarities and differences between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE). Typical examples are seen in different pronunciation but exact spelling, different spelling but same pronunciation, similar spelling and pronunciation but use in different contexts, same word but different meaning, different words but same meaning, use of syntax and punctuations and reference to collective nouns and pluralised adjectives (EUCLID 2021, 25-28). I found this uncovering a practical guide that will help me align my presentation in academic writing to my preferred English setting (SBE).

6) PLAGIARISM

In this section, the course pack introduces plagiarism as an essential requirement that an academic scholar needs to take very seriously. Plagiarism is 'when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34). It is a serious offence that can have damning consequences when detected. EUCLID 2021 considers an act of taking someone else words or ideas without appropriate credit or having someone write your essay and put your name as the writer (p. 34) as plagiarism which will attract consequences such as lowering grade or failing grade (p. 14) if detected. The section further clarifies that when a writer makes a citation, whether, in the form of quotes, paraphrases or reference to statistical data, appropriate credit will be required to acknowledge the source of the citation because it is unethical for the writer to claim someone else's work as theirs. This act or practice will constitute a breach of the principle of academic writing. I also learnt from this section that the best way to avoid plagiarism is to properly cite the source of any information or data referenced in the essay (EUCLID 2021, 34). To do this properly, two methods of citations were suggested: in-text and list of work approaches.

In-text citations refer to citations inserted within the text, while the list of work styles indicates when sources consulted in your essay are listed at the end of the paper. Further guidance is also provided on how to cite quotations properly, whether as part of the text (short quotation) or indented, especially when the quotes are longer than four lines (Euclid 2021, 35). Whichever form a writer chooses, it is advised not to use too many quotations to preserve the essay's originality. According to EUCLID 2021, quotations are effective when it carries substantial weight or when referencing an authority figure to advance an argument (36). While quotations may add credence, it is advisable not to overuse them; instead, consider paraphrasing, which is writing in your word even though

Commented [GK2]: Always used block letters when the word "University" is not used!

Deleted: p.

the idea is taken from another source. However, whether it is a quotation or paraphrase, it is essential to give credit to the source to avoid being caught up in plagiarism.

Deleted: in order

This section concludes by providing some examples to follow, especially as a EUCLID student. I found this a very helpful guide because it provides examples across all mediums, including how to cite books and online works and when and how to use footnotes for referencing (Euclid 2021, 38-39).

7) STYLE GUIDE

This chapter provides a quick summary of what a style guide is, why a writer needs to observe the use of a particular style, and the one recommended by EUCLID for its students. According to EUCLID 2021, style guides are different approaches writers can use to document their different kinds of writing (1). Every writer needs to align and be consistent with the elements of the chosen style, which is why many publishing companies provide a guideline on their preferred styles. Adherence to a particular writing style helps to keep the finished work coherent and consistent (EUCLID 2021, 41). Be it in technical, journalism or business writing, a style guide allows the writer to follow some basic rules and enable consistency of the final product with acceptable standards expected by their chosen publishers.

Deleted: p. 4

I understand from reading this section that writing style is broader in scope than grammar or the use of language. It usually covers areas such as sentence arrangement, layout, font usage, use of abbreviations, accepted terminologies and symbols, and general structure of the writing (EUCLID 2021, 41-42). The list is not exhaustive as it will be based on the preference of the publisher or company's acceptable elements. For example, while EUCLID will accept other internationally recognised styles and use of British English, it recommends that its students should follow the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and use American English in writing their essays.

8) CONCLUSION

This course exposed me to critical rules and guidance required for academic writing and presentation. Excellent academic writing must align with certain rules and procedures relating to the writer's specific writing styles. The course elucidates some steps to consider when preparing to write an academic essay: starting early, giving sufficient time for research, and making a plan to enable logical flow and presentation of ideas. It elaborates on the effective use of punctuation marks, abbreviations, and Latin expressions in academic essays. In addition, this course explains sufficiently that plagiarism is a grave academic offence with dire consequences, as well as states how EUCLID treats incidences of plagiarism when detected. ACA-401D course materials (both the coursepack and audio-visual materials) provide succinct detail about EUCLID's acceptable standards, which all its students are required to comply with when preparing their academic essays. These include using an appropriate template and style guide (Turabian) for their submissions,

such as the response papers, major papers, and dissertation. Finally, it offers a sample of how the course instructor reviews a typical response paper.

Deleted: R

Deleted: P

Deleted: M

Deleted: P

Deleted: D

Deleted: R

Deleted: P

REFERENCES

Britannica Dictionary. n.d. "Punctuation Online." Accessed on 19 September 2022. <https://www.britannica.com/dictionary/punctuation>.

Deleted: .

Cleenewerck, Laurent. 2021. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo video.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Gulma, Kabiru, 2021. *Instructor's Sample Review Tutorial*. YouTube video

Formatted: Font: Italic

Webster-Merriam Dictionary. n.d. "Punctuation Online." Accessed on 19 September 2022. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/punctuation>.

Deleted: .

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.